

Title: USE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Abstract. The article discusses the role of educational mobile applications in learning the English language. Special attention is paid to the didactic characteristics and capabilities of educational mobile applications. A comparative analysis of the Duolingo and Quizlet applications is presented.

Keywords: foreign language, information technology, mobile applications, modern learning, motivation.

Introduction. Currently, computers and other digital devices have become an integral part of every individual's life. Digital mobile devices have firmly established themselves not only in everyday life but are also widely used in the learning process. This is expressed both in the widespread use of interactive teaching tools and in the gradual integration of mobile phone applications into the learning process based on various platforms: Android, iOS, etc. Specially organized language learning at a university implies that the student should develop independently and motivate themselves to acquire new knowledge. However, unfortunately, currently developed language education programs for non-language majors inadequately reflect the issues of organizing foreign language teaching and the role of practical implementation of language culture as one of the main factors in education and upbringing of students in non-language majors. Mobile devices come to the aid of teachers and students to achieve this goal, which are successfully used in studying various academic disciplines, and foreign languages are no exception. The use of e-learning allows improving the quality of education by using rapidly replenishing global educational resources and by increasing the share of independent student work in mastering the material. Currently, mobile applications for learning foreign languages are gaining wide popularity. They have great potential in enhancing the effectiveness of the language learning process and are intended to significantly improve the process of language preparation for a wide range of learners, turning it from a serious laborious process into an exciting activity.

This topic is relevant and has been addressed in the works of such domestic researchers as M.V. Arkhipova, E.V. Vulfovich, I.N. Golitsyna, N.L. Polovnikova, N.V. Samokhina, O.V. Smolovik, and others. Learning using MIT abroad is also relevant. This problem was addressed by both foreign researchers such as K. Betti, V.M. Frank, S. Freynik, D. Richardson, and others. The use of tablet computers, smartphones, mobile phones, iPads,

iPhones, and similar devices for educational purposes has led to the formation within the concept of e-learning of a new direction - mobile learning of foreign languages (M- Learning - Mobile learning).

Presentation of the main material of the article. Currently, there are several definitions of mobile learning in foreign pedagogical literature, based on the technological features of mobile devices and the didactic possibilities provided by these technologies.

According to the MoLeNet project, mobile learning is the use of convenient portable mobile devices and wireless, always available technologies to support, optimize, and expand learning and teaching processes. According to another definition, mobile learning is the activity carried out regularly through compact, portable mobile devices and technologies that allow learners to become more productive by communicating, receiving, or creating information. In general, most researchers conclude that the uniqueness of mobile learning compared to traditional teaching methods and modern methods such as e-learning and blended learning lies in the fact that learners are not tied to a specific time and place but have access to study materials at any time, at their convenience. Additionally, mobile applications have several other advantages: intensification of independent activity, individualization of learning, increase in cognitive activity, and learning motivation. A significant advantage of mobile applications over "paper dictionaries" is their multimedia and hypertextuality. For example, hyperlinks in mobile applications can lead to the required resource immediately, increasing the intensity of learning. There are several popular mobile applications for learning English, among them are: Quizlet, Lingualeo, Duolingo, Memrise. The authors of the article conducted a comparative analysis of the Duolingo and Quizlet applications using specific criteria. To find out whether such applications are popular among students and to conduct their qualitative analysis, a survey was conducted, in which 250 students of the Faculty of Management and Socio-Technical Services of K. Minin Nizhny Novgorod State Pedagogical University aged 17 to 21 participated.

Table 1

Survey Results of Students

Question	Answer Options	Results (%)
1. Are you aware of mobile apps for	A) Yes B) No	A) 72 B) 28
learning English?		

2. If yes, do you use them?	A) Yes, regularly B) Yes, occasionally C) No	A) 35 B) 41 C) 24
3. If yes, which ones?	A) Duolingo B) Quizlet C) Lingualeo D) Memrise	A) 63 B) 25 C) 12 D) 0

4. Do you think these apps can help in learning English?	A) Yes B) Partially, as an additional source of knowledge C) No	A) 55 B) 39 C) 6
5. Where did you learn about these apps?	A) From friends B) On the Internet C) At school, work D) Through advertising	A) 18 B) 39 C) 9 D) 34
6. Are you interested in learning English using apps?	A) Yes B) No	A) 87 B) 13
7. Do you think using apps makes learning English easier?	A) Yes B) No C) I think there are not enough applications	A) 62 B) 7 C) 31
8. Would you prefer to learn the language using apps or textbooks?	A) I would prefer applications B) I would prefer a textbook C) I would prefer both options D) I think using both applications and a textbook is not enough	A) 33 B) 13 C) 45 D) 9
9. If you use an app to learn English, how often do you use it?	A) Daily B) 5-6 times a week C) 3-5 times a week D) 1-2 times a week E) Less than once a week	A) 11 B) 24 C) 18 D) 40 E) 7
10. If you use an app to learn English, have you noticed your progress?	A) Yes, I am satisfied with the result B) Yes, but the result is not sufficient C) No, I did not notice	A) 66 B) 21 C) 13

According to the survey results, it was found that the majority of students (about 70%) are aware of the existence of such applications and use them. The most popular among them are Duolingo and Quizlet. It was also revealed that a large portion of respondents either do not use them regularly (41%) or do not use them at all (24%). Only 35% of students study with the help of the application on a regular basis. Most respondents learned about these programs online (39%) or through advertising (34%), with only 9% learning about them at school or work. Thus, university students are poorly informed about

Of the apps analyzed in Table 1, the two most popular among students are Duolingo (63%) and Quizlet (25%). Duolingo is a language learning service designed to involve users in translating web pages, documents, and articles as they progress in their studies. This project was developed by Carnegie Mellon University professor Luis von Ahn (the creator of reCAPTCHA) and his graduate student Severin Hacker. The mobile app is freely accessible and serves as a tool for improving writing, speaking, reading, and listening skills for those learning new languages, including English. The learning approach is based on the principle of increasing difficulty with each successful lesson, requiring internet access for content download.

Quizlet, an online learning tool, was created in 2015 by 15-year-old Andrew Sutherland, a sophomore student in California. Initially designed to help study 111 French terms, Quizlet has since grown into one of the fastest-growing free educational platforms, with 30 million monthly users from approximately 130 countries. Quizlet allows users to create simple flashcards to effectively memorize and practice new vocabulary, view words or their translations, and listen to pronunciations. The app tracks user performance in real-time, highlighting incorrect terms to help users focus more on areas needing improvement.

The authors conducted both quantitative and qualitative analyses of these applications (see Table 2) and provided a detailed examination of each.

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Duolingo and Quizlet Mobile Applications

Criteria	Duolingo	Quizlet
1. Free learning	+	-
2. Interface convenience	+	-
3. Language practice capability	+	+
4. Interaction with other users	+	+
5. Gamification of learning	+	-
6. Access to theoretical base	+	+
7. Grammar practice capability	+	+
8. Ability to ask questions	+	+
9. Innovative learning methods	+	-
10. Material reinforcement	+	+
11. Programs for different levels	+	+
12. Creation of word groups	+	+
13. Sharing word groups	-	+
14. Selection of existing word groups	+	+
15. Transcription capability	-	-
16. Speech recording capability	+	+
17. Image addition capability	-	+
18. Statistic tracking	+	+
19. Situational lexical exercises	+	+

A comparative analysis demonstrates that both applications offer numerous advantages for learning English. However, Duolingo is more widely used. Quantitative analysis shows that Duolingo has higher usage rates, but Quizlet excels in qualitative aspects. The benefits of Duolingo include:

1. Free Access: The app offers a variety of language learning features free of charge, with unlimited usage, whether continuously or intermittently.
2. Extensive Forum: Users can interact and support each other, enhancing motivation and making the learning process more engaging.
3. Ease of Use: The tasks are straightforward, and the interface is designed to be intuitive, with familiar and understandable icons and labels.
4. Gradual Difficulty Increase: Tasks become progressively harder as users

advance. If an error is made, the question is repeated to reinforce learning and improve retention .

An independent study on Duolingo’s effectiveness was conducted in the fall of 2012 over eight weeks . Participants were required to use the app for at least 30 hours, with a minimum of 2 hours per session. Researchers predicted that daily sessions of 15 minutes would significantly impact progress, even for those who had never studied the language before. The study found that language skills improved by an average of 91.4%, and it took between 26 and 49 hours to learn the basics, depending on consistent usage of the platform .

Surveys among participants revealed the following motivations for learning a language:

1. Personal interest – 66.5%
2. Business/work – 14.5%
3. Travel – 8.8%
4. School/University – 8.3%
5. Other reasons (e.g., interest in languages, family, helping children with language learning) – 1.8% .

Another survey indicated high user satisfaction: 95.5% found the app easy to use, 92.4% felt it genuinely helped them learn the language, 87.9% were satisfied with their learning experience, and over 80% would recommend Duolingo to a colleague or friend .

Quizlet, another effective tool for language learning, offers a wide range of flexible and accessible resources that can be used anywhere. This internet resource includes various speech-based exercises:

1. Spelling practice
2. Tests with translation tasks (entering translations, selecting correct translations)
3. Flashcard creation
4. Matching words with definitions
5. The “Gravity” game, where users type words based on definitions displayed on the screen.

Quizlet aims to serve over 1.5 billion students worldwide. Its advantages include:

1. Monitoring student progress: Upgraded users (Quizlet Teacher) can track student achievements.
2. Quick results.
3. General availability.
4. The ability to create classes and monitor student performance.

5. Time-saving: Once entered, material can be reused for creating other sets.
6. Reusability: Sets can be reused across different groups and proficiency levels .

Conclusion: A comparative analysis reveals that both Duolingo and Quizlet offer substantial advantages for learning English. However, Duolingo appears to be more popular. While Duolingo excels in quantitative metrics, Quizlet surpasses in qualitative aspects. Duolingo's advantages include free usage, an extensive forum, user-friendly interface, and gradual complexity in tasks. Quizlet offers features like progress tracking, quick results, accessibility, class creation, time-saving, and versatility. Mobile language learning applications intensify language acquisition, aid in forming language patterns, and enhance grammar skills, thereby improving the quality of language education in universities. These apps can be utilized at various stages of skill development, leveraging their visual aids for effective learning. Thus, mobile language apps facilitate language learning, fostering communication skills and grammatical proficiency, thereby enhancing foreign language education in higher institutions.

Literature:

- Archipova M.V., Zhulina E.V., Shutova N.V. Information Society and Educational Process // Problems of Modern Pedagogical Education. 2018. № 59-1. P. 56-59

- Varshavskaya S.V. Using Mobile Reference Applications to Optimize English Language Learning Process / S.V. Varshavskaya // New Technologies in Foreign Language Teaching: Proceedings of the Scientific-Practical Conference. - Omsk: Omsk State University named after F.M. Dostoevsky, 2015. - P. 97-103.
 - Kaznacheeva S.N., Bondarenko V.A. Study of Readiness of Non-Language Students to Use Network Resources in Learning Foreign Languages // Bulletin of Minin University. 2018. Vol. 6, №2. P. 8. DOI: 10.26795/2307-1281-2018-6- 2-8
 - Malushko E.Yu. Electronic Course as a Form of Innovation Implementation in Higher Education // Bulletin of Minin University. 2019. Vol. 7, №3. P. 2.
 - About Duolingo Company [Electronic resource]. Duolingo.com: informational portal. URL: <https://www.duolingo.com/info> (accessed: 06.11.2018).
 - Quizlet Application: How to Use? [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <http://fb.ru/article/468557/prilojenie-quizlet-kak-polzovatsya>
 - Samokhina N.V. Using Mobile Technologies in English Language Teaching: Development of Traditions and Search for New Methodological Models / N.V. Samokhina // Fundamental Research. - 2014. - №6. - P. 591-595.
-
- Smolovik O.V., Grishunina M.A. Using ICT to Increase Student Motivation in Foreign Language Learning // In collection: Scientific Discussion: Issues of Philology and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages collection of articles based on the materials of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. Nizhny Novgorod State Pedagogical University named after K. Minin. 2018. P. 113-116.
 - Smolovik O.V. Features of Students' Emotional Well-being in the Process of Learning a Foreign Language // Problems of Modern Pedagogical Education. 2018. № 60-4. P. 463-465.
 - Titova S.V. Mobile Learning Today: Strategies and Perspectives / S.V. Titova // Bulletin of Moscow University. Series 19: Linguistics and Intercultural Communication. - 2012. - №1. - P. 9-23.
 - What is "Quizlet" and How Can It Be Used? [Electronic resource]. Quizlet.com: informational portal. URL: <https://quizlet.com/ru/help/2444083/what-is-quizlet-and-how-can-i-use-it>
 - Beatty K. Mobile Language Learning: the World in Our Hands // Anaheim University, USA. - 2015 - №17 [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: www.anaheim.edu/schools-and-institutes/graduate-school-of-education/diploma-in-tesol/243-about/faculty-and-staff/tesol-faculty/886-ken-beatty-phd-ken-beatty-phd (accessed: 06.11.2018).

- Frank V.M., Freynik S., Richardson D.L. Technologies for Foreign Language Learning: A Review of Technology Types and Their Effectiveness // Center for Advanced Study of Language, University of Maryland, College Park, MD. - 2014. - №1. - Vol. 27 [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/153571> (accessed: 30.05.2019).
- Grego J., Vesselinov R. Duolingo Effectiveness Study – Final Report / J. Grego, R. Vesselinov / SC: Statistics Department University of South Carolina, 2012. – 24 p.
- Traxler J. Current State of Mobile Learning / J. Traxler // Mobile Learning: Transforming the Delivery of